

Supplementary document

Charts 1 and 2 present the characteristics and findings of the selected articles. Whenever applicable, the NV and/or passive solar heating strategies employed were identified.

Chart 1 - Characteristics of the selected articles

Strategy	Reference	Research location climate type	Research techniques	Measured or calculated variables	Main conclusions
Cross-ventilation	Xu <i>et al.</i> (2019)	Cfa	Computer simulation	Air velocity, total mass flow through doors, and total volume flow through doors	This study concluded that the reduction of doors and windows affects the performance of NV, altering airflow and wind speed inside the classroom. The increase in the number of occupants intensifies air turbulence; and the opening of two doors, even with only half of the windows open, maintains effective ventilation. The larger the window opening area, the greater the exhaust wind speed.
Cross-ventilation	Rodríguez-Vidal <i>et al.</i> (2022)	Cfb	Environmental measurement and estimation through calculation	Air temperature, relative humidity, air velocity, and CO ₂ concentration	This experiment demonstrated that the use of a real-time monitoring system, combined with user engagement, contributed to the improvement of IAQ and thermal comfort in classrooms at the University of the Basque Country during winter and spring. The proposed methodology showed potential for expansion with additional sensors and for integrating NV strategies in educational buildings without mechanical systems, promoting NV and awareness of IAQ.
Cross-ventilation	Zhang <i>et al.</i> (2022)	Cfa, Dfa, Dwa, Cwb and Aw	Environmental measurement, estimation through calculation and computer simulation	Air temperature, dry-bulb temperature, relative humidity, air velocity, and ventilation rates (VR)	This study concluded that the adoption of a cross-ventilation channel between classrooms and interior corridors improves the performance of NV in classrooms and helps reduce the mean age of air. The results indicate that NV performance is more efficient when the channel is located at the bottom of the partition, and that the channel area positively influences airflow, with larger areas promoting better ventilation conditions.
Cross-ventilation	Poza-Casado <i>et al.</i> (2021)	Cfb	Environmental measurement, computer simulation and estimation through calculation	Air temperature, relative humidity, air velocity, CO ₂ , Total volatile organic compound (TVOC), Particulate Matter (PM _{1.0} , PM _{2.5} and PM ₁₀) concentrations, Air Changes per Hour (ACH),	This study concluded that air infiltration has a significant impact on IAQ and NV in higher education classrooms in Spain. It is important that the air infiltration rate be estimated in real buildings and considered in IAQ and NV efficiency analyses in order to enable more accurate assessments, avoid underestimations in the analyses, and ensure more rigorous diagnoses of ventilation and health conditions in educational environments.

				barometric pressure, and age of the air	
Cross-ventilation	Monge-Barrio <i>et al.</i> (2022)	Cfb	Environmental measurement, estimation through calculation, student questionnaires, and interviews with teachers	Air temperature, relative humidity, air velocity, previous activity, clothing insulation, and CO ₂ concentration	Before and during the pandemic, the schools analyzed maintained acceptable IAQ levels through NV, despite indoor temperatures being below the ideal range in winter. Clear protocols and teacher involvement were effective in reducing CO ₂ concentrations. The authors recommend that schools develop a plan to improve IAQ by implementing cross ventilation in classrooms, installing CO ₂ and temperature monitoring systems in representative rooms, and improving the building envelope.
Cross-ventilation	Sarbu and Pacurar (2015)	Cfb	Environmental measurement, computer simulation, estimation through calculation, questionnaires, and student attention tests	Air temperature, relative humidity, black globe temperature, and CO ₂ concentration	This study concluded that indoor environmental quality directly influences academic performance, being affected by variables such as temperature, CO ₂ , and lighting. Simulations and measurements demonstrated that improvements in ventilation and thermal control contribute to more suitable learning environments in university classrooms.
Cross-ventilation and single-sided ventilation	Mumovic <i>et al.</i> (2009a)	Cfb and Cfc	Environmental measurement and estimation through calculation	CO ₂ concentration and VR	The study evaluated ventilation rates in four secondary schools in England based on the performance criteria defined by Building Bulletin 101 (BB101). The results show that compliance with ventilation parameters was achieved due to occupant behavior rather than the standard ventilation strategy adopted. The authors propose a balanced methodology for assessing VR, considering the complexity of school environments and the need for clear guidelines, training, and reliability in ventilation system performance.
Cross-ventilation, single-sided ventilation and use of automated windows	Mumovic <i>et al.</i> (2009b)	Cfb and Cfc	Environmental measurement and estimation through calculation	Air temperature, wet-bulb globe temperature, dry-bulb temperature, relative humidity, air velocity, and CO ₂ concentration	This study concluded that achieving adequate thermal comfort, ventilation, and acoustic performance in schools is a complex task. Naturally ventilated classrooms partially met the criteria, while those with mechanical ventilation presented issues related to noise and cold draughts. One-third of the classrooms exceeded CO ₂ limits, and indoor temperatures were generally higher than those projected. The results indicate the need for more effective design guidelines for school buildings.
Cross-ventilation and single-sided ventilation	Korsavi, Montazami and Mumovic (2020a)	Cfb	Environmental measurement, estimation through	Air temperature, radiant temperature, relative humidity,	The study concluded that IAQ in naturally ventilated primary schools in the United Kingdom (UK) shows variations associated with factors

			calculation and student questionnaires	air velocity, and CO ₂ concentration	related to occupancy (number of students per classroom and window-opening frequency). CO ₂ concentrations were found to exceed recommended limits, especially in rooms with lower volume per occupant and insufficient ventilation; however, occupant interaction with the building proved more significant, suggesting the need to train occupants to adopt more adaptive behaviors.
Cross-ventilation and single-sided ventilation	Korsavi, Montazami and Mumovic (2020b)	Cfb	Environmental measurement and student questionnaires	Air temperature, radiant temperature, relative humidity, air velocity, and CO ₂ concentration	This study concluded that occupant-related and building-related factors influence the effectiveness of NV and must be considered in the design process. To ensure adequate ventilation rates in schools with NV, the authors recommend: a comprehensive understanding of contextual factors by designers; attention to window design parameters, considering seasonal differences; and occupant engagement through appropriate adaptive behaviors. The study highlights the responsibility of regulators, designers, managers, and users in maintaining IAQ.
Cross-ventilation and single-sided ventilation	Korsavi, Montazami and Mumovic (2020c)	Cfb	Environmental measurement and observation	Air temperature, relative humidity, air velocity, and CO ₂ concentration	This study concludes that the effectiveness of NV in primary schools depends on contextual, design, and behavioral factors that must be considered integrally in the design process. It is recommended that designers take into account factors such as noise and pollution. Occupants should be guided on window use, as improper operation compromises thermal performance even in environments with high NV potential.
Cross-ventilation	Hwang, Huang and Chen (2021)	Cfa	Computer simulation and estimation through calculation	Air temperature, operative temperature, wind speed, VR, sensible cooling load, heat gain through window glass, sensible cooling load, air density, balance temperature for closed windows, and balance temperature for open windows	This study demonstrated that building design criteria, such as window-to-wall ratio, orientation, and shading, are decisive for the thermal and energy performance of schools in hot and humid climates, being fundamental to the effectiveness of ventilation systems and the achievement of comfortable indoor conditions.
Cross-ventilation	Bajc, Todorović and Papadopoulos (2016)	Cfa	Environmental measurement	Air temperature, relative humidity and CO ₂ concentration	This study is part of a broader research on indoor environmental quality and energy performance of buildings, aiming to correlate IAQ with occupant performance in offices and classrooms. The work highlights

					the challenges of assessing indoor environmental quality in naturally ventilated buildings and indicates initial possibilities for conclusions within this context.
Cross-ventilation	Dugaria, Pernigotto and Gasparella (2021)	Cfa	Environmental measurement and estimation through calculation	Air temperature and CO ₂ concentration	This study concluded that, although the schools analyzed meet legal requirements, they present unsatisfactory conditions in terms of thermal comfort and air quality. The results indicate high CO ₂ levels and occupant discomfort, reinforcing the need for stricter guidelines and specific actions to ensure healthy and adequate school environments.
Cross-ventilation and single-sided ventilation	Korsavi, Jones and Fuertes (2022)	Cfb	Environmental measurement and observation	Air temperature, radiant temperature, relative humidity, air velocity, and CO ₂ concentration	The behavior of students in UK primary schools significantly influences IAQ, thermal comfort, and the schools' energy consumption. During the non-heating season, increases in operative and outdoor temperatures lead occupants to open windows more frequently, while during the heating season, increases in indoor and outdoor humidity result in window closure. The results suggest that lowering operative temperature and CO ₂ levels during the non-heating season can be achieved by opening windows, and that energy waste during the heating season could have been avoided by reducing the setpoint temperature and improving user awareness.
Cross-ventilation	Chiang, Hsu and Huang (2013)	Cfa	Computer simulation and estimation through calculation	Air velocity, airflow path, mean age of air (MAGE), and ACH	This study concluded that physical elements such as openings, corridors, and shading devices affect the distribution of indoor airflow and the MAGE in the breathing zone of school buildings. Indoor airflow patterns are more influenced by the layout of the inlet fenestration than by the outlet layout. The depth and position of the blinds are less critical on lower floors, and the use of slotted blinds improves airflow patterns.
Cross-ventilation and night ventilation	Tagliabue <i>et al.</i> (2020)	Cfa and Cfb	Computer simulation	Air temperature, operative temperature, convective heat transfer coefficient for humans, radiative heat transfer coefficient for humans, and energy demand	This study concluded that thermal discomfort during summer is common in European schools across various climate types, indicating the need for retrofitting and improvements in the design phase. Passive strategies such as thermal inertia control, shading, and night ventilation showed effective results in temperate climates. In hot climates, the use of high-efficiency air conditioning systems is recommended to manage temperature peaks.
Cross-ventilation	Hu <i>et al.</i> (2023)	Cfa	Environmental measurement, estimation	Air temperature, relative humidity, and air velocity	This study concluded that in cold indoor environments during winter, university occupants exhibited high

			through calculation, and student questionnaires		thermal adaptability under different heating types. NV combined with heating resulted in lower average temperatures but encouraged non-mechanical adaptive behaviors. The optimal temperature for comfort was estimated between 22.3 °C and 24.0 °C. Heating reduced air conditioner use by up to 55%, indicating potential for energy savings.
Cross-ventilation and single-sided ventilation	Hama <i>et al.</i> (2023)	Cfb	Environmental measurement	Air temperature, relative humidity, VR, CO ₂ , PM ₁ , PM _{2.5} and PM ₁₀ concentrations, and ACH	Combined ventilation (natural + mechanical) was more effective in reducing PM compared to NV. PM and CO ₂ concentrations were associated with occupancy. Rooms with larger volumes showed higher ventilation rates per person, even with lower ACH. The results reinforce the importance of NV, room typology, and IAQ monitoring to mitigate exposure to pollutants in school environments.
Cross-ventilation and single-sided ventilation	Rawat and Kumar (2024)	Cfb	Environmental measurement and teacher questionnaires	Air temperature, relative humidity, air change rate (ACR), CO ₂ , PM ₁ , PM _{2.5} and PM ₁₀ concentrations	This study examined the effects of different interventions on IAQ and thermal comfort in two classrooms of a school near a major highway in the UK. Results showed that NV, especially through continuous or cross-ventilation, proved more effective than partial ventilation or air purifiers alone in improving air quality and thermal comfort. However, its effectiveness was reduced in winter or in classrooms exposed to outdoor pollution. In such cases, a combined strategy, using air purifiers during occupancy and NV during non-occupancy, was recommended.
Cross-ventilation	Ma <i>et al.</i> (2023)	Cfa	Environmental measurement, estimation through calculation, and student questionnaires	Air temperature, relative humidity, illuminance, and CO ₂ concentration	This study indicated that low carbon dioxide concentration had a positive impact on the cognitive abilities evaluated, while relative humidity showed negative effects on short-term memory and attention. Compact environments exhibited great variability in classroom indoor physical environment (CIPE) and volatile learning performance (LP). The findings may inform the design of different types of classrooms, including moderate window openings to maintain good relative humidity, reflective wall finishes, and configurations to control CO ₂ concentrations.
Cross-ventilation and	Figueroa-Lopez <i>et al.</i> (2023)	Cfb	Environmental measurement	Air temperature, relative humidity,	All classrooms met the thermal comfort criteria established by the EN (European Norm) 16798, with a

single-sided ventilation				and CO ₂ concentration	higher percentage of comfort recorded during the summer. Gymnasiums showed greater vulnerability due to their large volume and the difficulty in achieving hygrothermal comfort. Classrooms with similar construction characteristics exhibited different performances. School S1, without a ventilation system, achieved satisfactory hygrothermal comfort in both summer and winter. The results indicate that buildings with NV and mechanical ventilation can achieve good thermal performance.
Cross-ventilation	Niu <i>et al.</i> (2023)	Cfa	Environmental measurement, estimation through calculation and computer simulation	Air velocity, turbulent kinetic energy, air pressure, and age of air	This study concluded that the presence of external trees alters the thermal performance of NV. Compared to buildings without trees, airflow, pressure distribution, and air age within the building can be affected, with a reduction in flow rate. Classrooms with a horizontal layout became cooler as canopy spacing increased. In vertically arranged classrooms, the effect was influenced by the vertical characteristics of the species. Metasequoias demonstrated a lower negative impact on NV compared to camphor trees.
Cross ventilation and single-sided ventilation	Papadopoulos <i>et al.</i> (2023)	Cfb	Environmental measurement, computer simulation, estimation through calculation, and student questionnaires	Air temperature, radiant temperature, relative humidity, air velocity, CO ₂ , volatile organic compounds (VOCs), aldehydes, ozone concentrations, wind speed, wind directions, barometric pressure, ACH, and VR	This study concluded that simulation analysis provides more stable results compared to the tracer gas method, but both analyses indicate that NV in the classrooms studied is inadequate and below the levels recommended by standards during the COVID-19 period. The results showed that increasing ventilation rates combined with mask use reduces the risk of infection and improves IAQ without compromising thermal comfort.
Cross-ventilation	Kumar, Rawat and Tiwari (2023)	Cfb	Environmental measurement and estimation through calculation	Air temperature, relative humidity, illuminance, sound pressure level, CO ₂ , PM _{2.5} , PM ₁₀ , and secondary pollutant concentrations	This study concluded that classroom occupancy increases PM ₁₀ and CO ₂ concentrations, and that the effectiveness of air purifiers depends on their location. The use of multiple purifiers in strategic positions enhances particle removal. It is recommended to place exhaust fans near the ceiling, purifiers at children's breathing height, and to use real-time pollutant monitors to optimize air quality in naturally ventilated classrooms.
Cross-ventilation	Weng <i>et al.</i> (2023)	Cfa	Environmental measurement, estimation through	Air temperature, relative humidity, illuminance, sound pressure	This study, conducted in China concluded that green universities have better indoor environmental quality and greater occupant

			calculation and questionnaires	level, CO ₂ , and PM _{2.5} concentrations	satisfaction, while traditional buildings demonstrate better health performance. CO ₂ concentration negatively impacts learning efficiency, whereas desk illuminance has a positive effect. The control of temperature, ventilation, and CO ₂ is essential to reduce SBS symptoms and improve student performance.
Cross-ventilation	Lavtižar, Fikfak and Fink (2023)	Cfb	Environmental measurement	Air temperature, relative humidity, CO ₂ , PM _{2.5} , and PM ₁₀ concentrations	The study reinforces the effectiveness of NV in improving indoor air quality in classrooms, particularly through cross-ventilation strategies. However, limitations arise during colder periods or in areas with high outdoor pollution, compromising both thermal comfort and continuous ventilation. The findings indicate that locations less exposed to pollutants allow for longer window opening times and a better balance between ventilation and thermal comfort. Therefore, NV strategies should account for both air quality and occupants' thermal well-being to ensure healthier and more efficient school environments.
Cross-ventilation	Hwang, Liao and Chen (2022)	Cfa	Environmental measurement, estimation through calculation, and computer simulation	Air temperature, cooling energy, and CO ₂ concentration	This study concluded that in schools located in hot and humid climates, the use of air conditioning improves thermal comfort but reduces academic performance due to poor IAQ. The ideal combination to maximize performance and minimize energy consumption involves temperatures between 23 °C and 25 °C and ventilation rates above 20 L/s-person.
Cross-ventilation	Vignolo <i>et al.</i> (2022)	Cfa	Environmental measurement and estimation through calculation	Air temperature, relative humidity, CO ₂ concentration, and ACH	This study concluded that the classroom has the potential to reach very high ventilation rates with cross ventilation; however, during normal occupancy, this occurs only for short periods, with daily average ACH values remaining low due to occupants' thermal discomfort, which prevents them from operating the windows. Periodic ventilation proved effective in reducing the airborne transmission risk of SARS-CoV-2, reconciling thermal comfort and IAQ in naturally ventilated environments.
Cross-ventilation	Liu and Shi (2022)	Cfa	Environmental measurement, estimation through calculation and student questionnaires	Air temperature, globe temperature, relative humidity, air velocity, illuminance, sound intensity and CO ₂ concentration	This study proposed a human comfort evaluation model for university classrooms, considering operative temperature, illuminance, noise, and CO ₂ concentration. Through objective measurements and subjective questionnaires, weights were assigned to each parameter, highlighting temperature as the most influential factor. The model allows for the adjustment of indoor

					environmental parameters to maximize comfort, serving as a tool for designing more efficient and personalized educational buildings.
Cross-ventilation and hydroponic rooftop greenhouses	Ledesma, Nikolic and Pons-Valladares (2022)	Cfb	Computer simulation and estimation through calculation	Air temperature, operative temperature, relative humidity, heat flux, and CO ₂ concentration	This study concluded that the co-simulation method effectively assessed the impact of rooftop farms on free-running educational buildings. Integrated rooftop greenhouses offered the greatest thermal and environmental benefits, while edible green roofs provided the best balance between comfort improvement and energy efficiency. The effectiveness of rooftop farms depends on building envelope, geometry, and solar exposure.
Cross-ventilation and single-sided ventilation	Avella <i>et al.</i> (2021)	Cfb	Environmental measurement and interviews with teachers and staff	Air temperature, relative humidity, and CO ₂ concentration	This study evaluated the effectiveness of a CO ₂ -based visual alert system and concluded that it can improve air quality in schools, but its effectiveness depends on user behavior and usage conditions. The system proved effective in the high school with in-person classes and full occupancy. Analyses in the other schools were inconclusive due to low occupancy, student age, and remote learning during the COVID-19 pandemic. The study suggests future testing with tracer gas and window automation.
Cross-ventilation	Haddad <i>et al.</i> (2021)	Cfa	Environmental measurement, estimation through calculation and student questionnaire	Air temperature, wind speed, relative humidity, and CO ₂ and formaldehyde concentrations	This study evaluated IAQ, thermal comfort, and the effect of a DCV system with air extraction in secondary school classrooms in a subtropical region of Australia, demonstrating that split-type air conditioning systems do not ensure adequate ventilation and IAQ. The installation of a CO ₂ -controlled ventilation system (DCV) with air extraction resulted in a significant reduction in CO ₂ and volatile organic compound (VOC) levels, as well as an improvement in air exchange rates.
Cross-ventilation and single-sided ventilation	Korsavi, Montazami and Mumovic (2021)	Cfb	Environmental measurement and student questionnaire	Air temperature, relative humidity, air velocity, and CO ₂ concentration	This study concluded that children's perception of IAQ in classrooms is associated with CO ₂ levels and operative temperature. High values of CO ₂ and operative temperature compromise children's acceptance of IAQ, even when concentrations are within acceptable limits. The results indicate the need for simultaneous control of CO ₂ and temperature by the building management system, recommending that standards and regulations consider both parameters in IAQ assessment.
Cross-ventilation	Burman, Kimpian and Mumovic	Cfb and Cfc	Environmental measurement, estimation	Air temperature, dry-bulb temperature,	This study concluded that the five evaluated school buildings present CO ₂ emissions associated with energy

	(2018)		through calculation and questionnaires	relative humidity, VR, fossil-thermal performance, electricity use, daily electrical load, and CO ₂ concentration	performance that fall short of the design targets, revealing shortcomings in energy efficiency policies. Issues related to procurement and operation compromised efficiency, air quality, and thermal comfort. Overall, the study concluded that a building will not reach its performance potential unless post-occupancy actions are undertaken to optimize the building and train users in the correct use of its systems.
Cross-ventilation and single-sided ventilation	Chatzidiakou, Mumovic and Summerfield (2015)	Cfb	Environmental measurement and estimation through calculation	Air temperature, relative humidity, CO ₂ , PM ₁ , PM _{2.5} , PM ₁₀ , NO ₂ , O ₃ , TVOCs, VOCs, fungal and bacterial group concentrations, and ACH	Based on a holistic approach to analyzing IAQ policies in schools, including the implementation of low-cost measures to reduce pollutant levels in classrooms, the study provides insights despite the sample size limitations. The results serve as a basis for decision-making regarding the design, retrofit, and renovation of school buildings. The authors recommend the inclusion of regular IAQ assessments in building standards, as well as campaigns comparing indoor and outdoor pollutants in school environments.
Cross-ventilation, increased solar gain through windows and high thermal mass for heating	Filippin <i>et al.</i> (2007)	Cfa	Environmental measurement, computer simulation and estimation through calculation	Air temperature, relative humidity, clothing insulation, natural gas consumption, metabolic rate and solar radiation on horizontal surfaces	This study, conducted in a passive solar school in Argentina, concluded that the scholar building demonstrated good thermal performance, with adequate indoor temperatures and a 90% reduction in energy consumption compared to conventional schools. Simulations and measurements indicated that solar and metabolic gains were sufficient to maintain thermal comfort, with minimal use of auxiliary heating. The importance of architectural design and proper indoor environment management is emphasized to maximize thermal performance efficiency.
Cross-ventilation, Single-sided ventilation and high thermal mass	Chatzidiakou <i>et al.</i> (2015)	Cfb	Environmental measurement and estimation through calculation	Air temperature, relative humidity, CO ₂ , PM ₁ , PM _{2.5} , PM ₁₀ , total volatile organic compounds (TVOCs), VOCs, benzene, toluene, limonene, pinene, trichloroethylene (T3CE), tetrachloroethylene (T4CE), naphthalene, formaldehyde concentrations, ACH, and VR	This study identified occurrences of overheating in eight classrooms facing south, southeast, and east during the non-heating season, and average CO ₂ concentrations above 1500 ppm in four classrooms of contemporary schools. It concludes that poor indoor air quality results from inadequate school operation practices, highlighting the need to include the analysis of specific pollutants, in addition to CO ₂ , to ensure healthy school environments.

Cross-ventilation	Zivelonghi and Kumar (2024)	Cfa	Environmental measurement and estimation through calculation	Air temperature, relative humidity, CO ₂ concentration, ACH, and VR	This study, conducted in an aging middle school building in Northern Italy, concludes that the use of Signaled Manual Airing (SMA) systems with alarms based on CO ₂ levels and acoustic reinforcement can enhance IAQ in classrooms through occupant-driven actions, although with limitations in cold climates. The authors recommend collecting field data and conducting local analyses prior to implementing SMA, and also advocate for the development of hybrid and automated ventilation systems.
Cross-ventilation and Single-sided ventilation	Kumar <i>et al.</i> (2024)	Cfb	Environmental measurement and estimation through calculation	Air temperature, relative humidity, CO ₂ , PM ₁ , PM _{2.5} , PM ₁₀ concentrations, ACH, and VR	This study concluded that factors such as occupancy, room volume, and type of ventilation significantly influence IAQ. During periods of high occupancy, PM ₁₀ and CO ₂ levels were higher compared to unoccupied periods. Mixed ventilation reduced PM ₁₀ and CO ₂ levels compared to NV. Larger rooms showed better IAQ and higher ventilation rates. Mixed ventilation, strategic classroom location, and proper floor maintenance are recommended.
Cross-ventilation and single-sided ventilation	Nehr <i>et al.</i> (2024)	Cfb	Environmental measurement and estimation through calculation	Air temperature, relative humidity, CO ₂ , PM _{2.5} , TVOC concentrations, VR, Occupant-specific supply air flow rate, energy demand, Area-specific annual energy demand, room volume per occupant, window opening area per occupant and per ground area, room opening area per occupant and per ground area.	This study concluded that the analyzed classrooms present inadequacies in their construction parameters to meet the normative requirements for efficient NV, resulting in poor IAQ, particularly regarding CO ₂ concentration. NV limited by window opening area and high occupancy rate was insufficient, leading to significant energy losses during the heating period. The authors recommend decentralized mechanical ventilation systems as a solution to improve IAQ and student performance.
Cross-ventilation	Munckton and Rajagopalan (2024)	Cfb	Environmental measurement and estimation through calculation	Air temperature, radiant temperature, relative humidity, air velocity, CO ₂ concentration, VR, clothing insulation and metabolic rate	In this study, conducted in five Kindergartens in Australia, it was found that CO ₂ levels exceeded the values considered acceptable according to the literature. Median values of PMV and PPD indicated thermal discomfort for children and teachers. Classrooms with mixed ventilation showed lower CO ₂ concentrations, although in some cases, excessive NV compromised thermal comfort. The installation of CO ₂ sensors with alarms is recommended as an initial measure to improve indoor conditions.

Cross-ventilation	Zhou <i>et al.</i> (2024)	Cfa	Environmental measurement, computer simulation and estimation through calculation	Air temperature, air velocity, airflow path, mean age of air, CO ₂ concentration, and VR	By simulating and analyzing airflow patterns and CO ₂ levels under various negative pressure ventilation (NPV) configurations, the study demonstrates that controlled ventilation, especially the Upward Supply Upward Return model with windshields, can significantly mitigate cross-infection among students. Furthermore, NPV systems can help maintain more stable indoor temperatures and reduce localized thermal discomfort caused by stagnant or poorly ventilated air
Cross-ventilation	Correia, Amorim and Santamouris (2024)	Cfb, Cwb (dry-winter subtropical highland climate), Cfa, Aw (tropical savanna climate with a dry winter), Af (tropical rainforest climate), Bsh (hot semi-arid climate) and Am (tropical monsoon climate)	Environmental measurement and computer simulation	Air temperature, dry-bulb, operative temperature and heat balances	This study concluded that the standard model of Brazilian public schools can achieve thermal comfort levels in all eight bioclimatic zones through passive strategies, without the use of air conditioning. The FNDE standard model, with a heavy flat roof and insulated walls, proved compatible with the country's climatic diversity, requiring only minor adjustments. The most effective strategies include the use of super cool roofs and the proper sizing of openable areas for ventilation.
Cross-ventilation	Park and Lee (2020)	Cfa	Environmental measurement and computer simulation	Air temperature, relative humidity, air velocity and CO ₂ concentration	The study demonstrated that an improved NV strategy can significantly reduce energy consumption by approximately 30% compared to a mechanical ventilation system with variable refrigerant flow (VRF), while providing comparable performance. However, its practical implementation requires further investigation, taking into account factors such as internal heat gains, CO ₂ emissions, and room usage schedules.
Cross-ventilation	Paschoalin Filho <i>et al.</i> (2022)	Cfa	Environmental measurement, test application and student questionnaire	Air temperature, air relative humidity, clothing frequency and CO ₂ concentration	This study found that students were able to perceive differences in indoor environmental conditions, particularly in relation to air quality and thermal comfort. Among the tested scenarios, the one without air conditioning or proper ventilation (DWcAcoff) was considered the most uncomfortable. Despite CO ₂ levels and indoor temperatures remaining within acceptable limits, students still reported discomfort, highlighting the importance of effective NV and thermal regulation. The findings underscore the need for improved classroom design to support student

					well-being and comfort, reinforcing the role of architecture in creating healthier and more conducive learning environments.
Cross-ventilation	Yang <i>et al.</i> (2019)	Cfa	Environmental measurement and computer simulation	Air velocity, air age and area ratio of air age (AOA)	This study analyzed how classroom position, building layout, and wind direction impact NV and thermal comfort in "line" type school buildings. Simulations showed that outside corridors and larger rooms improve airflow, and classrooms near the wind inlet (0°–35°) have better ventilation. In subtropical climates, aligning buildings with prevailing winds and placing key rooms near the inlet can enhance comfort. These findings support more effective use of NV in school design.
Cross-ventilation and night ventilation	Pegg, Cripps and Kolokotroni (2005)	Cfb	Environmental measurement, computer simulation, estimation through calculation and observation	Air temperature, air relative humidity, wind speed and direction and CO ₂ concentration	The study showed that thermal comfort and adequate ventilation were achieved without mechanical cooling, due to passive strategies like night ventilation and a well-designed atrium. Despite warmer conditions on the second floor, controlling roof-light openings based on wind direction improved performance. NV also enhanced air quality by diluting indoor pollutants. While acoustics in open-plan classrooms were less favorable, overall results support the effectiveness of passive design in meeting comfort and ventilation goals in educational buildings.
Single-sided ventilation and automated windows	Grygierek <i>et al.</i> (2023)	Cfb	Computer simulation and estimation through calculation	Air temperature, operative temperature, relative humidity, CO ₂ concentration, and ACH	This study, which was conducted using a typical Polish classroom as a reference, revealed that NV was insufficient to ensure adequate IAQ and thermal comfort during windless periods, potentially raising CO ₂ concentrations to critical levels. Intelligent window opening, combined with optimized control systems, improves thermal comfort and air exchange rates. The combination of controlled ventilation, mask use, air purifiers, and reduced occupancy proved effective in maintaining IAQ and minimizing infection risks.
Single-sided ventilation	Lala <i>et al.</i> (2022)	Cfa	Environmental measurement, estimation through calculation and student questionnaire	Air temperature and relative humidity	This study concluded that the proposed multi-task deep learning model, DeepComfort, effectively predicts three thermal comfort metrics (Thermal Sensation Vote, Thermal Preference Vote and Thermal Comfort Vote) simultaneously and outperforms six single-task models. Validated with data from five schools, 14 naturally ventilated classrooms, and 512 students, the model demonstrated high accuracy and generalization

					capability, despite the challenges associated with children's subjective responses. The authors indicate as future work the expansion of the model to additional comfort metrics and adaptive behaviors.
Single-sided ventilation	Marschall and Burry (2019)	Cfb	Computer simulation and estimation through calculation	Air and design temperature	This study proposed an operational strategy based on adaptive occupancy, using sensor networks to dynamically prescribe usage schedules according to microclimatic variations, with the aim of optimizing thermal comfort and energy efficiency. The results indicated that adaptive occupancy allows for a greater degree of architectural diversity, increases thermal comfort, and reduces the use of mechanical systems.
Single-sided ventilation,	Stazi, Naspi and D'Orazio (2017)	Cfa	Environmental measurement, estimation through calculation and observation	Air temperature, mean radiant temperature, solar radiation, relative humidity, air velocity, wind velocity, wind direction, and CO ₂ concentration	This study concluded that indoor temperature is the main factor influencing window use, while outdoor temperature has a lesser impact and CO ₂ showed no significant correlation. Openings occur more frequently in the early morning, influenced by routine. It is recommended that simulations include user behavior, and further research is needed for validation in different contexts.
Single-sided ventilation, automated windows and ventilation stacks	Dhalluin and Limam (2012)	Cfb	Environmental measurement, and student and teacher questionnaire	Air, operative, and globe temperatures, global solar radiation, relative humidity, air velocity, wind speed, wind direction, surface temperature, illuminance, precipitation, CO ₂ , PM ₁₀ , PM _{2.5} , and PM ₁ concentrations, air exchange rate, and energy consumption	By comparing four distinct ventilation modes in adjacent university classrooms, the research highlights the effectiveness of NV, particularly when controlled by temperature and lighting conditions, during summer. In contrast, no single approach demonstrated clear superiority in winter, suggesting that seasonal adaptability remains a challenge. The findings indicate that with thoughtful parameter control, NV can serve as a viable and energy-efficient solution for enhancing comfort and air quality in academic environments.
Single-sided ventilation	Perna <i>et al.</i> (2011)	Cfa	Environmental measurement, estimation through calculation, and student and teacher questionnaires	Air and average radiant temperatures, global solar radiation, relative humidity, air velocity, wind speed, surface temperature, total net solar radiation, surface temperature, CO ₂ concentration, tracer gas	This study evaluated NV strategies in a classroom of an Italian school, highlighting that the absence of mechanical ventilation systems, common in the country's schools, results in poor IAQ, thermal discomfort, and high energy consumption. Experimental results demonstrated that user-controlled ventilation alone is inefficient, indicating the need to implement optimized solutions to meet IAQ, thermal comfort, and energy

				concentration, and PM _{10-0.1} concentrations.	efficiency requirements in accordance with standards.
NV system with heat recovery	Dorizas <i>et al.</i> (2018)	Cfb	Environmental measurement, estimation through calculation and observation	Air temperature, relative air humidity, air velocity, ACH, percentage of time with windows closed and CO ₂ concentration	Considering that the objectives of the study involved evaluating the performance of a passive ventilation system with heat recovery (PVHR) installed in two classrooms, the environmental monitoring indicated that both indoor temperatures and CO ₂ levels were in accordance with the UK guidelines for schools. Indoor temperatures remained within the recommended limits set by the BB101 standard. It was found that both passive heat recovery systems operated in purge mode for a significantly greater proportion of time during the heating season than in bypass mode, thereby limiting heat recovery.
NV system with heat recovery and wind tower	O'Connor, Calautit and Hughes (2014)	Cfb	Computer simulation and wind tunnel experiment	Air temperature, air velocity, air supply rate per person, pressure loss, pressure drop across the rotary thermal wheel	In this study, the incorporation of a rotary thermal wheel into a wind tower does not significantly compromise the ventilation rate delivered to the indoor environment, provided that the inlet air velocity exceeds 3 m/s. The ventilation rate achieved was consistent with the guidelines for classrooms with minimum occupancy density, but insufficient for larger class sizes at lower inlet velocities. Thermal analysis indicated a heat recovery of up to 3 °C, which could result in energy savings of up to 20%.
NV system with heat recovery	Liu, Jimenez-Bescos and Calautit (2023)	Cfb	Computer simulation and estimation through calculation	Air temperature, VR, wind speed, pressure contour, metabolism rate and CO ₂ concentration	The study demonstrated that the wind tower with thermal heat recovery (THR) can provide effective ventilation and maintain adequate CO ₂ levels; however, its performance may vary depending on occupant density and external conditions. While it contributes positively to indoor air quality, thermal comfort may be compromised due to lower air velocities, highlighting the need for adaptive strategies to ensure efficient ventilation without undermining occupants' thermal well-being.
Automated windows	Heebøll, Wargocki and Toftum (2018)	Cfb	Environmental measurement	Air, operative, and globe temperatures, global solar radiation, relative humidity, air velocity, wind speed, wind direction, surface temperature, illuminance, precipitation,	This study concluded that automated windows can significantly reduce CO ₂ concentrations in classrooms, especially when combined with an exhaust fan, whereas manual window opening or the use of heat recovery units did not yield significant improvements. The lowest CO ₂ levels were observed in classrooms equipped with mechanical ventilation or automatic windows paired with an exhaust fan. Temperatures remained

				CO ₂ , PM ₁₀ , PM _{2.5} , and PM ₁ concentrations, air exchange rate, and energy consumption	within the recommended comfort range.
Automated windows	Gao, Wargocki and Wang (2014)	Cfb	Environmental measurement, estimation through calculation and student questionnaire	Air temperature, air relative humidity, estimated ventilation rates and CO ₂ concentration	It was observed that mechanical ventilation provided higher air exchange rates in the context studied, but did not lead to improved occupant perceptions. In contrast, classrooms equipped with automatically operable windows and an exhaust fan received more favorable evaluations, maintaining low CO ₂ levels and adequate ventilation. Window opening behavior appeared to be habitual among students and was primarily influenced by outdoor weather conditions, being less frequent during the winter and almost constant in warmer periods
Automated windows and solar chimney	DeBlois and Ndiaye (2015)	Cfb	Computer simulation	Air temperature, air flow rate, air velocity and HVAC energy consumption and savings	A high-performance solar chimney was developed using computational methods to enhance thermal comfort. EnergyPlus simulations showed up to 5% HVAC energy savings and 1,200 hours of suitable NV. The study highlights the need to optimize system performance and engage occupants through a combination of manual and automated controls. Automated windows and exhausts prevent overlap between mechanical and NV, with teachers deciding when to switch systems, guided by an educational indicator light.
Exhaust chimney	Mankibi <i>et al.</i> (2006)	Cfb	Environmental measurement, computer simulation and estimation through calculation	Air temperature, air relative humidity, air pressure, solar radiation wind velocity, wind direction and VOC and CO ₂ concentrations	This study conducted a cross-simulation analysis to compare the performance of three ventilation systems and to evaluate the consistency of two numerical models, HYBCELL1.0 and SPARK, in predicting indoor conditions under various control strategies. Findings indicate that, particularly in winter and spring, the hybrid ventilation system provided superior indoor air quality and adequate thermal comfort, despite slightly higher energy consumption. In summer, energy demand for hybrid ventilation was reduced, although CO ₂ concentrations were marginally higher. The results underscore the effectiveness of hybrid strategies, which integrate NV, in maintaining thermal comfort.
Windcatcher	Liu <i>et al.</i> (2024)	Cfb	Environmental measurement	Air temperature, air velocity, ACH, VR, supply (air)	This study examined a prototype windcatcher's performance in cold climates using field tests and CFD

			and computer simulation	temperature, supply (air) velocity in Channel, MAGE and air change effectiveness (ACE)	(Computational Fluid Dynamics) simulations. The authors found that static models may miss real-world variability. Classroom simulations indicated that higher wind speeds can cause excessive ventilation, leading to heat loss and greater heating needs. Windcatchers alone may not suit cold climates without strategies to balance comfort and energy use. In this context, heat recovery, thermal storage, or adaptive controls could help.
Ventilation stacks and Windcatcher	Kolokotroni and Katsoulas (2002)	Cfb	Environmental measurement, computer simulation and estimation through calculation	Air temperature, air velocity and CO ₂ concentration	This study evaluated the performance of passive thermal stacks in a school building in South East England, to assess their effectiveness in NV. Higher indoor temperatures were linked to greater heat gains and shorter stack heights, highlighting the need for improved airflow paths in high-load spaces like IT rooms. While air exchange rates did not differ significantly between rooms with and without stacks during one period, this was likely due to occupant adjustments, which have limitations under certain conditions. The stacks contributed significantly to total airflow, acting as key exhaust routes.
Windcatcher	Nejat <i>et al.</i> (2024)	Cfb	Computer simulation	Operative temperature, air relative humidity, air velocity, metabolic rate and clothing level	This study examined how upper wing wall (UWW) angles affect NV in a two-sided roof-mounted windcatcher using CFD simulations. Results showed a non-monotonic trend, with 30° as the optimal angle. This angle improved airflow, air changes, and air quality while reducing stagnant zones. Compared to a horizontal UWW, the 30° angle boosted ventilation efficiency by up to 12% and surpassed ASHRAE 62.1 standards across wind speeds. The findings emphasize optimizing UWW geometry for effective passive ventilation.
Windcatcher	Mavrogianni and Mumovic (2009)	Cfb	Environmental measurement, computer simulation, estimation through calculation and student questionnaires	Air temperature, air relative humidity, dry bulb temperature, ACH, VR, and CO ₂ concentration	This study examines the use of windcatcher systems in classrooms with variable and elevated internal heat loads. The study found that winter thermal comfort was generally adequate, but indoor temperatures often exceeded targets due to poor heating control and limited ventilation. In summer, NV was partly effective, but future climate warming may worsen overheating, highlighting the need for improved ventilation management and adaptive measures.
Windcatcher	Jones and Kirby (2012)	Cfb	Environmental measurement	Air temperature, air relative	This study concluded that the implementation of a top-down NV system, such as the Windcatcher, as

				humidity and CO ₂ concentration	part of a well-designed NV strategy, can significantly improve ventilation rates in classrooms. However, during the winter season, ventilation is insufficient due to the limited use of the system, which compromises indoor air quality and underscores the need for adjustments, such as activating the ventilator in response to indoor CO ₂ levels, to maintain both thermal comfort and healthy indoor conditions.
Wind tower	Rabeharivelo, Kavraz and Aygün (2022)	Cfa	Computer simulation and estimation through calculation	Operative temperature, air relative humidity, air velocity, metabolic rate and clothing level	The study concluded that although wind towers are effective in promoting NV, they may compromise thermal comfort in classrooms, particularly due to high airflow velocities at the level of seated occupants. The tower opening size was the most influential factor in performance, and its reduction contributed to improved thermal sensation. To ensure greater comfort, more effective control of airflow is required, such as the use of adjustable dampers.
Displacement NV	Wang <i>et al.</i> (2014)	Cfb	Environmental measurement, computer simulation and estimation through calculation	Air temperature, air velocity, air heat loss, and CO ₂ concentration.	The effectiveness of displacement NV in ensuring thermal comfort and maintaining IAQ was evaluated in a low-energy school Building. The findings highlight the influence of thermal buoyancy on airflow and temperature distribution, which contributes to thermal stratification and helps lower pollutant concentrations. Adjustments in supply air temperature and velocity were shown to enhance ventilation performance and reduce CO ₂ levels, although excessively high airflow may negatively affect occupant comfort
Night ventilation	Sengupta <i>et al.</i> (2023)	Cfb	Environmental measurement, computer simulation and estimation through calculation	Air temperature, dry bulb temperature and heating degree-hours	This study introduced an approach to classify and quantify the impact of different thermal shocks on overheating resilience in two classrooms. The findings indicated that heatwaves (HWs) are considered the most critical events for nZEB (nearly zero energy buildings) under future climate scenarios. HWs reduce the diurnal temperature variation, thereby compromising the effectiveness of passive cooling strategies. The differences observed between the analyzed spaces were mainly attributed to increased solar gains, highlighting the need for more robust design strategies to ensure thermal comfort.
Night ventilation and increased solar	Irulegi <i>et al.</i> (2017)	Cfb	Environmental measurement, computer	Air temperature, relative air humidity, and	This study analyzed energy retrofit strategies at the School of Architecture in San Sebastián, based

gain through windows			simulation, estimation through calculation and student and teacher questionnaires	heating energy demand	on students' thermal comfort preferences. The results showed that students feel comfortable at lower temperatures than those indicated by conventional models. In summer, manual NV (4 ACH) enabled thermal comfort without air conditioning. In winter, measures such as the elimination of thermal bridges, heat recovery, and improvement of window frames allowed for up to a 62% reduction in heating demand, while respecting the architectural constraints of the building.
Night ventilation and high thermal mass for heating	Dasgupta, Prodromou and Mumovic (2012)	Cfb and Cfc	Computer simulation and questionnaires	Air temperature and energy consumption	This article, conducted out in England, concludes that the new schools studied do not meet the basic criteria for energy performance and IAQ. The analysis of studies and feedback from industry professionals' highlights failures in policy, design, and commissioning processes. It also points out that the lack of understanding of how to design learning spaces suited to current pedagogical practices compromises the effectiveness of low-carbon school buildings.
Diffuse ceiling ventilation and shading with transparent insulation	Bugenings <i>et al.</i> (2022)	Cfb	Computer simulation	Air temperature and primary energy consumption	This study, carried out in Aalborg, Denmark, demonstrated that the combination of diffuse ceiling ventilation and double-skin façade is an effective solution for school retrofitting, promoting thermal and acoustic comfort, efficient ventilation, and reduced energy consumption, while being technically and economically feasible for modernization.
High thermal mass for heating	Su <i>et al.</i> (2022)	Cfb	Environmental measurement	Air temperature and relative humidity	This study concluded that school buildings in New Zealand with lightweight structures and low insulation presented cold and humid indoor environments during winter, compromising students' thermal comfort and health. Retrofitting with insulation increased average indoor temperatures and reduced relative humidity but did not eliminate high thermal variation. The addition of thermal mass proved more effective, maintaining temperature and humidity within ideal comfort and health ranges, and is recommended as a strategy to improve thermal performance in schools located in temperate and humid climates.

Source: the authors.

Chart 2 - Characteristics of the selected articles that address NV in classrooms but do not specify the NV strategies

Reference	Research location climate type	Research techniques	Measured or calculated variables	Main conclusions
Montazami, Wilson and Nicol (2012)	Cfb	Environmental measurement and estimation through calculation	Air temperature, aircraft noise level (dB), VR and CO ₂ concentration	According to the findings of this study, window-based NV alone is inadequate for maintaining comfort and air quality in primary schools under flight paths, particularly in summer. With UK summers projected to warm by up to 7 °C, overheating risks will grow, worsened by poor ventilation. To address this, architects should consider strategies like solar gain control, high thermal mass materials, night ventilation, and the use of ventilation shafts.
Huang and Hwang (2016)	Cfa and Aw	Computer simulation and estimation through calculation	Air temperature, ACH, Internal heat gain, cooling energy, energy saving potential	The study evaluated ventilation systems in classrooms of Taiwanese schools. It was observed that NV alone was insufficient to maintain thermal comfort throughout the year, whereas hybrid ventilation effectively eliminated overheating and improved indoor conditions. The findings emphasize that thermal comfort should not be compromised for energy savings, as it directly affects students' health and learning. Key design elements, such as window orientation and shading, significantly impact energy performance and comfort.
Andamon, Rajagopalan and Woo (2023)	Cfb	Environmental measurement and estimation through calculation	Air temperature, relative humidity, observation and CO ₂ concentration	According to this study, many Victorian schools depend on NV, which is often inadequate due to weather variability and design. While air conditioners are being added for comfort, they usually don't improve ventilation. CO ₂ -based measurements reveal ventilation challenges but help assess air quality. The findings stress the need for better ventilation, improved classroom design, teacher training, and greater awareness of its impact on health and learning, key steps toward pandemic-resilient schools.
Liu, Yang and Niu (2021)	Cfa	Environmental measurement, computer simulation and estimation through calculation	Area ratio of age of air (AOA), wind pressure gap and wind pressure	The research explored how classroom position and wind direction impact NV in "L"-shaped school buildings. Simulations showed that rooms closer to the wind inlet have better airflow, while corner rooms often have the poorest ventilation. Buildings with longer wings, especially the 1:2 ratio, offer better ventilation on the long side. These findings help inform design decisions to enhance thermal comfort through improved NV.
Vilcekova <i>et al.</i> (2017)	Cfb	Environmental measurement, estimation through calculation and questionnaires with students and staff	Air temperature, air relative humidity, CO ₂ and PM _{2.5} and PM ₁₀ concentrations, equivalent A-weighted noise level and illumination	The study assessed indoor environmental quality in a Slovak special needs school, highlighting issues such as high CO ₂ levels, particulate matter, low lighting, and sound discomfort. Students reported feeling overheated, likely due to their high activity levels. Despite limited staff responses, both students and staff showed symptoms related to poor air quality. The findings emphasize the need for improved NV and thermal comfort to ensure healthier, more supportive learning environments.
Nagy <i>et al.</i> (2019)	Cfb	Environmental measurement, estimation through calculation and student questionnaires	Air temperature, air relative humidity, energy consumption, CO ₂ and PM ₁ , PM _{2.5} and PM ₁₀ concentrations and equivalent sound pressure level	This study assessed a historic building's indoor environment, focusing on occupant health and comfort. While relative humidity and PM ₁₀ levels were within acceptable limits, CO ₂ concentrations slightly exceeded recommended values, indicating a need for better ventilation. Thermal comfort concerns were reflected in reports of fatigue and heavy-headedness. The findings highlight the importance of improving NV and indoor conditions in historic buildings to enhance occupant well-being.

Chen and Chan (2019)	Cfa	Environmental measurement, estimation through calculation and questionnaires with students and staff	Air temperature, air relative humidity, air velocity, metabolic rate and clothing level	Through this study, it was examined thermal comfort under air conditioning and NV in a hot-humid climate, using a portable system to collect 257 responses. Results showed that the PMV index underestimated occupants' thermal sensations, especially in naturally ventilated spaces, suggesting discomfort was higher than predicted. The findings highlight the need to refine thermal comfort models and account for factors like solar radiation to better reflect real conditions, particularly when using NV.
Belafi <i>et al.</i> (2018)	Cfa	Environmental measurement, estimation through calculation, interviews with teachers and observation	Air temperature, dry-bulb temperature, CO ₂ level and window opening	This study explored differences in window use behavior in two similar school classrooms in Hungary, highlighting how NV practices vary. In one classroom, window operation was closely linked to indoor and outdoor temperatures, supporting thermal comfort. In the other, no clear connection to environmental conditions was found, with social factors playing a stronger role. These results emphasize that both environmental and behavioral aspects influence NV and thermal comfort.
Tognon <i>et al.</i> (2023)	Dfb (Humid continental climate with warm summers), Cfa and Csa (Hot-summer Mediterranean climate)	Environmental measurement and computer simulation	ACH, thermal energy and electrical energy	This study analyzed the energy performance and infection risk associated with ventilation systems in residential and school buildings across different climates. Simulations demonstrated that prioritizing NV over mechanical systems significantly reduced cooling demand, fan energy consumption and infection risk, particularly in classrooms, where fan energy savings reached up to 86% in warmer climates. NV also delivered higher airflow rates, enhancing indoor air quality and comfort. These findings emphasize the benefits of well-controlled hybrid systems that favor NV, improving thermal comfort and indoor health while reducing energy use.
Liu, Yu and Essah (2023)	Cfa	Environmental measurement, estimation through calculation and questionnaire	Air temperature, globe temperature, air relative humidity and air velocity	This study found that students in unheated university classrooms during winter tolerated lower indoor temperatures (average 13.9 °C), often feeling cold but adapting through clothing adjustments. Preferred temperatures were slightly warmer than neutral, and thermal comfort was influenced by personal factors like past experience and expectations. These results suggest that passive design and NV can support thermal comfort without heating systems in similar educational environments.
Burridge <i>et al.</i> (2023)	Cfb	Environmental measurement	Air temperature, air relative humidity and CO ₂ concentration	The research assessed NV and thermal conditions in UK classrooms during the COVID-19 pandemic. Data from 36 classrooms revealed elevated CO ₂ levels indicating insufficient ventilation despite seasonal expectations. While climate played a role, behavioral factors, such as changing adherence to safety protocols, also influenced ventilation rates. The findings emphasize the importance of ensuring adequate NV to support both indoor air quality and thermal comfort in learning environments.
Genjo (2022)	Cfa	Environmental measurement, estimation through calculation and staff questionnaires	Air temperature, globe temperature, air relative humidity, illuminance, equivalent noise level and CO ₂ and PM _{2.5} concentration	This investigation involving 15 nursery schools in Japan revealed concerns related to thermal comfort and indoor air quality. Summer temperatures in some rooms exceeded 30 °C, while winter temperatures near the floor were too low due to poor insulation and circulation. Ventilation was often inadequate, with high CO ₂ and particle levels, especially in winter. These findings stress the need for improved insulation, better ventilation, and specific indoor environmental standards to ensure infant comfort and health.

Moazzen, Karagüler and Ashrafian (2021)	Cfa, Cfb and Csa	Computer simulation and estimation through calculation	End-use energy consumption, life cycle energy consumption, Life cycle CO ₂ emission, energy costs, running costs, replacement costs, deviation of monthly electricity consumption and deviation of monthly natural gas consumption	The study evaluated the life cycle and energy performance of educational buildings, with a focus on reducing carbon emissions and improving comfort conditions. By applying the proposed approach, Turkey's educational facilities could achieve lower primary energy consumption and enhanced indoor comfort. The findings highlight the importance of cost-optimal, nearly zero-energy buildings for environmental and economic benefits. The research also emphasizes the role of insulation materials in thermal comfort and energy efficiency, suggesting the need to consider alternative materials.
Predescu and Dunea (2021)	Cfb	Environmental measurement, computer simulation, estimation through calculation and student questionnaires	Air relative humidity, wet bulb globe temperature, vapor pressure, exchange rate, PM ₁ , PM _{2.5} , PM ₄ , PM ₁₀ , TPM (Total Particulate Matter) and CO ₂ concentrations	The study demonstrated that combining thermal microclimate data with occupant characteristics helps assess comfort in university classrooms. PM ₁ levels were within acceptable ranges under thermally comfortable conditions. Indoor air quality was impacted by disinfectant use during the COVID-19 pandemic. Despite limitations, the findings highlight the value of integrating air quality and thermal comfort data to support healthier indoor learning environments.
Miao, Gangoells and Tejedor (2023)	Cfa	Environmental measurement and estimation through calculation	Operative temperature, air relative humidity and CO ₂ concentration	A predictive model using Random Forest was developed to estimate IAQ and thermal comfort in naturally ventilated classrooms, based on easily accessible data. With over 460 hours of field measurements across multiple seasons in 32 classrooms in Catalonia, the model showed high accuracy for thermal comfort. Key predictors included occupancy levels, window and door operation, and outdoor conditions, while building characteristics had limited influence. The findings highlight the importance of occupant behavior in maintaining thermal comfort in naturally ventilated schools.
Custódio, Ghisi and Rupp (2024)	Cfa	Environmental measurement, estimation through calculation and student questionnaires	Air temperature, relative air humidity, operative temperature, globe temperature, thermal sensation, air velocity, clothing insulation, metabolic rate and body weight	This study assessed student thermal comfort in naturally ventilated and air-conditioned university classrooms in southern Brazil. It was observed that students felt more comfortable in naturally ventilated spaces and preferred temperatures higher than those predicted by standard models, suggesting energy savings are possible without compromising comfort due to students' adaptive capacity.
Custódio <i>et al.</i> (2024)	Cfa	Environmental measurement, estimation through calculation and student questionnaires	Air temperature, air relative humidity, operative temperature, mean radiant temperature, thermal sensation, globe temperature, air velocity, clothing insulation, metabolic rate, body mass index and body weight	Through this study, it was explored whether socioeconomic factors influence thermal comfort among university students. By controlling for environmental and personal variables, no significant differences were found in students' thermal sensation across income levels, work status, courses, or ethnicity. Despite different socioeconomic backgrounds, students reported similar thermal perceptions under comparable conditions, highlighting that thermal comfort may be more strongly shaped by environmental factors than by social context.
Eichholtz, Kok and Sun (2024)	Cfb	Environmental measurement	Air temperature, PN ₁₊ and CO ₂ concentrations	Following school reopening's during the pandemic, both natural and mechanical ventilation improved indoor air quality. Naturally ventilated classrooms showed greater CO ₂ and particle reductions, highlighting the value of simple behavioral measures. These findings stress the ongoing importance of ventilation strategies to ensure thermal comfort and healthy learning environments.

Zhang and Bluysen (2021)	Cfb	Environmental measurement, estimation through calculation and questionnaire with students and teachers.	Air temperature, air relative humidity, electricity consumption, gas consumption, electricity consumption per unit of area, gas consumption per unit of area, teachers' activity index; illuminance; sound pressure level and CO ₂ concentration	The analysis of nine Dutch primary schools revealed that energy savings can be achieved without compromising indoor comfort. Schools with moderate energy use had the best perceived indoor environmental quality (IEQ), suggesting that well-balanced building features and teacher practices can enhance both energy efficiency and thermal comfort. These findings highlight the potential for combining comfort and sustainability in educational settings.
Tang, Ding and Singer (2020)	Cfa	Environmental measurement, estimation through calculation and questionnaire	Air temperature, air relative humidity, illuminance, sound pressure and PM _{2.5} , PM ₁₀ and CO ₂ concentrations	The evaluation of ten nonresidential buildings in Chongqing showed that thermal comfort was better in winter, though dryness was a common complaint. The PMV-PPD model often failed to reflect actual comfort when local variations occurred. Visual glare and low humidity affected satisfaction, and acoustics received the lowest ratings—especially in shopping malls. The results highlight the need to improve thermal comfort assessment and IEQ conditions across building types.
Asif and Zeeshan (2020)	Cfa	Environmental measurement, computer simulation and estimation through calculation	Air temperature, air relative humidity, ACH, VR and CO ₂ concentration	The study monitored IAQ and thermal comfort in naturally ventilated classrooms across two seasons. Despite the use of fan heaters and air conditioning units, indoor temperature and humidity often exceeded comfort thresholds. Ventilation was also found to be insufficient, with CO ₂ levels frequently surpassing ASHRAE limits during occupancy. The results highlight that existing systems failed to ensure thermal comfort or adequate air quality, reinforcing the need for climate-responsive indoor environmental controls in schools.
Fabozzi and Dama (2020)	Cfa	Environmental measurement, estimation through calculation and student questionnaires	Air temperature, air relative humidity, air velocity, clothing insulation and CO ₂ concentration	This study examined thermal comfort in 16 university classrooms in Milan. Finger's model predicted comfort well in air-conditioned rooms, while both Finger's and the Adaptive model worked for naturally ventilated rooms. However, EN 15251's adaptive comfort temperatures didn't match students' preferences where they lacked control. Many students were satisfied even when outside standard comfort ranges, showing that thermal comfort perception is complex.
Korsavi and Montazami (2020)	Cfb	Environmental measurement, estimation through calculation, student questionnaires and observation	Air temperature, air relative humidity, air velocity and radiant temperature	This study, conducted in the UK, shows that children tend to have lower comfort temperatures than adults and often feel overheated, especially during heating seasons due to fewer adaptive behaviors. Teachers usually control classroom conditions based on their own comfort, not the children's. To improve thermal comfort and energy use, schools should support adaptive actions by both teachers and students and encourage better communication about thermal preferences.
Korsavi and Montazami (2019)	Cfb	Environmental measurement, student questionnaires and observation	Air temperature, operative temperature, radiant temperature, air relative humidity, air velocity, illuminance, clothing insulation and CO ₂ concentration	The study validated a child-friendly questionnaire to assess thermal comfort and adaptive behaviors in schools. It captures children's personal thermal responses but is less suitable for environmental actions, such as window use. To overcome this, combining the questionnaire with observational forms is suggested, offering a comprehensive method to study how children experience and adapt to indoor thermal conditions.

Kim and Dear (2018)	Cfa and Cfb	Environmental measurement, estimation through calculation and student questionnaires and observation	Air temperature, operative temperature, neutral temperature and clothing insulation	This study, carried out in Australia, shows that children preferred cooler temperatures than those predicted for adults, and their comfort range was notably wider. As temperatures rose, students favored active cooling over passive strategies like adjusting clothing. While younger students adapted their clothing to the thermal environment, older students did not. The availability of air conditioning also reduced students' use of other adaptive behaviors, highlighting the importance of considering children's thermal comfort needs in classroom design.
Zečević, Husika and Džaferović (2018)	Cfa	Environmental measurement	Air temperature, air relative humidity and CO ₂ concentration	The study highlights critical ventilation issues in educational buildings, particularly during winter. High CO ₂ levels were frequently recorded, due to limited window use in colder months. Summer conditions allowed more frequent NV, improving both air quality and temperature. Optimal thermal comfort was generally maintained around 21-22 °C, but poor ventilation often compromised air quality. The findings emphasize the need for balanced energy strategies that do not sacrifice thermal comfort or air quality.
Mihlayanlar, Öztuna and Büyükakın (2017)	Cfa	Environmental measurement and estimation through calculation	Air temperature, radiant temperature, air relative humidity and air velocity	This study evaluated thermal comfort in three Trakya University classrooms during the heating season. Most indoor conditions complied with ASHRAE and ISO (International Organization for Standardization) standards; nevertheless, Classroom A, which faces south, exhibited slightly elevated temperatures. Results highlight the importance of thermal comfort for student performance, health and energy efficiency.
Maciel <i>et al.</i> (2017)	Cfa	Computer simulation	Air operative temperature, discharge coefficient, incident radiation and airflow	By using CFD to determine precise discharge coefficients for five shading configurations, the study shows how shading geometry affects airflow and indoor conditions. Simulations using corrected Cd values revealed significant differences in airflow and comfort periods, especially in designs with dense shading slats. Results suggest that accurate Cd values are essential to avoid underestimating airflow resistance, which directly influences thermal comfort.
Schibuola, Scarpa and Tambani (2016)	Cfa	Environmental measurement and estimation through calculation	Air temperature, ACH and CO ₂ concentration	This analysis emphasizes that frequent, short window openings are effective for improving IAQ and maintaining thermal comfort. The study recommends a practical, user-driven approach: equipping classrooms with CO ₂ monitors to raise teachers' awareness. This enables real-time self-management of ventilation based on both air quality and thermal comfort, supporting energy savings without compromising occupant well-being.
Kalimeri <i>et al.</i> (2016)	Cfa	Environmental measurement, estimation through calculation and observation and student questionnaires	Air temperature, air relative humidity, PM _{2.5} , PM ₁₀ , Benzene, Trichloroethylene, Tetrachloroethylene, Pinene, Limonene, HCHO, NO ₂ , O ₃ , and CO ₂ concentrations	This study assessed indoor air quality in three primary schools in Greece, identifying key pollutants and their sources. Despite generally low health risks, inadequate ventilation was a major concern, affecting both air quality and thermal comfort. Seasonal variations and limited window use contributed to poorer indoor conditions. The findings highlight the importance of regular ventilation and occupant behavior in maintaining healthier, more comfortable classroom environments.
Tomić <i>et al.</i> (2014)	Cfa	Environmental measurement, computer simulation, estimation	Air temperature, air relative humidity and CO ₂ concentration	This study assessed thermal comfort and air quality in classrooms. Three scenarios were analyzed: a closed room, a cooled room, and a naturally ventilated room. In both the closed and cooled classrooms, CO ₂ levels reached up to 5,200 ppm, indicating poor ventilation

		through calculation and observation and student questionnaires		and resulting in high PMV and PPD values. In contrast, the open-window scenario showed much better thermal comfort, with near-neutral PMV and low dissatisfaction. The study supports the introduction of fresh air through façade openings to improve thermal comfort and IAQ.
Corgnati, Ansaldo and Filippi (2007)	Cfb	Environmental measurement, estimation through calculation and student questionnaires	Air temperature, air relative humidity, operative temperature, mean air velocity and standard deviation of air velocity, plan radiant temperatures and clothing levels.	The study evaluated thermal comfort in university classrooms outside the heating season by combining environmental measurements with students' subjective responses. Results showed that slightly warm or neutral environments were generally well accepted, with fewer requests for temperature changes compared to previous winter studies. The findings highlight seasonal differences in thermal comfort perception and suggest that adaptive comfort models may better reflect occupants' real experiences.
Hellwig <i>et al.</i> (2008)	Cfb	Environmental measurement, teacher questionnaires and interviews with staff	Air temperature and CO ₂ concentration	The study analyzed indoor environmental conditions in two German schools and found that several classrooms experience thermal discomfort. Poor insulation and lack of effective shading contributed to these issues. Window use for ventilation was limited, especially in colder months, with no night or early morning ventilation observed. These findings highlight the need for better building systems and ventilation strategies to ensure consistent thermal comfort.
Corgnati, Filippi, and Viazzo (2007)	Cfa	Environmental measurement, estimation through calculation and student questionnaires	Air temperature, air relative humidity, operative temperature, mean radiant temperature and air velocity	According to this study, which applied a field-based methodology to assess thermal comfort in Italian university and high school classrooms during the heating season, slightly warm or neutral thermal conditions were generally well accepted, with many students preferring slightly warm environments. In colder conditions, more students expressed a desire for warmer temperatures. The findings emphasize the importance of aligning thermal comfort models with real occupant feedback to better support comfortable learning environments.
Yao, Liu, and Li (2010)	Cfa	Environmental measurement, estimation through calculation and questionnaire	Air temperature, air relative humidity, air velocity and clothing insulation	In this study, it was found that the university students tolerated a wider temperature range than predicted by conventional models, with a clear preference for warmer environments. Psychological adaptation played a key role when behavioral and physiological adjustments were insufficient. Thus, the research concludes that international standards like ASHRAE 55-2004 do not align with local needs, suggesting the development of a region-specific comfort range.
Griffiths and Eftekhari (2008)	Cfb	Environmental measurement and estimation through calculation	Air temperature, cloud cover, pressure, air relative humidity, wind speed and direction, VR, ACH and CO ₂ concentration	This research investigated the ventilation performance of a naturally ventilated classroom to monitor the CO ₂ levels. It was found that maintaining indoor air quality below 1500 ppm CO ₂ often required additional ventilation solutions. A 10-minute purge could significantly lower CO ₂ levels without causing discomfort, but was not enough for consistent air quality.
Lei and Shao (2023)	Cfa	Environmental measurement, computer simulation, estimation through calculation and questionnaire.	Air temperature, air relative humidity, dry bulb temperature, air velocity, clothing insulation and metabolic rate.	This study proposed a predictive model for thermal sensation in naturally ventilated indoor spaces, employing a Deep Belief Network (DBN) approach. The model achieved high accuracy and stability in predicting thermal sensations, by incorporating environmental and occupant-related parameters. The results highlight the DBN model's strong adaptability to the dynamic and variable nature of naturally ventilated spaces.

Yılmaz <i>et al.</i> (2022)	Cfa	Computer simulation and estimation through calculation	Air temperature, operative temperature, primary energy use, Useful daylight illuminance, indoor noise level, reverberation time and Life-cycle cost	As stated in this study, which analyzed classroom designs with varying window sizes, focusing on thermal comfort, NV, and overall performance, smaller apertures improve comfort in temperate, humid climates, challenging current design norms. Thermal comfort also benefits from heating setback strategies during unoccupied hours. Early design choices, such as orientation and adaptive façades, are key to ensuring comfortable, naturally ventilated environments.
Wood <i>et al.</i> (2024)	Cfb	Environmental measurement and estimation through calculation	Air temperature, VR and CO ₂ concentration	This study examined CO ₂ levels and indoor temperatures in 190 UK classrooms during Autumn 2023. Most classrooms maintained stable indoor temperatures due to heating, but CO ₂ levels rose during colder weather, indicating reduced NV. While most schools stayed within CO ₂ limits, a few showed consistently high levels, highlighting localized ventilation issues. Primary, fee-paying, and less-deprived schools generally had better air quality. The findings stress the need for targeted ventilation improvements that maintain comfort, especially in winter, and support continued long-term monitoring.
Catalina, Damian and Vartires (2024)	Cfa	Environmental measurement	Air temperature, air relative humidity, air velocity, noise level and CO ₂ concentration.	This study evaluated the effectiveness of decentralized ventilation systems in classrooms over a one-month period, comparing them to conditions without mechanical ventilation. The results showed that these systems significantly improve indoor air quality by keeping CO ₂ levels below recommended thresholds, which is essential for student health and cognitive performance. However, a drawback observed was the drop in indoor humidity, particularly in winter, highlighting the need for humidifiers to maintain thermal comfort. Compared to naturally ventilated classrooms, mechanically ventilated spaces showed more stable thermal and IAQ conditions. Overall decentralized systems present a practical and efficient solution for improving thermal comfort and NV performance in schools.
Nowak-Dziesko, Mijakowski and Müller (2024)	Cfb	Environmental measurement, computer simulation and estimation through calculation	Air temperature, air relative humidity and CO ₂ concentration, ventilation air flow, air heating power demand	According to the research, the analyzed classroom experienced poor indoor air quality due to high CO ₂ levels during occupancy, mainly caused by the low efficiency of the NV system during the heating season. Simulations showed that indoor air conditions remained inadequate throughout winter. While mechanical ventilation could improve air quality and thermal comfort, it would raise energy demand. Therefore, integrating heat recovery into mechanical systems is essential to balance improved ventilation and energy efficiency.
Wang <i>et al.</i> (2024)	Cfb	Environmental measurement	Air temperature, air relative humidity, air velocity, proportion of time extant heaters were in operation and CO ₂ concentration	This study evaluated the effectiveness of retrofitting Solar Air Heaters (SAHs) in naturally ventilated classrooms across six New Zealand primary schools during winter. SAHs helped maintain indoor temperatures within the thermal comfort and relative humidity range for most of the school day. The combined use of SAHs and existing heaters reduced CO ₂ concentrations and enhanced ventilation without relying solely on non-renewable energy.
Deng <i>et al.</i> (2024)	Cfa	Environmental measurement, computer simulation and estimation	Air velocity, viral load, viral particle level, quanta emissions and CO ₂ concentration	The analysis demonstrates that opening windows and doors significantly enhances NV, leading to substantial reductions in CO ₂ levels and airborne infection risk in university classrooms. Although enhanced ventilation improves air quality and thermal comfort, the study

		through calculation		warns that airflow redistribution must be carefully managed to avoid increasing exposure near infected individuals. It also supports the use of CO ₂ sensors as reliable indicators for ventilation control. These findings underscore the importance of optimizing NV strategies, especially in settings where mechanical systems are insufficient.
Summa <i>et al.</i> (2024)	Cfa	Environmental measurement and estimation through calculation	Air temperature, air relative humidity and CO ₂ concentration	The study evaluated indoor air quality and thermal conditions in classrooms with controlled mechanical ventilation (CMV) across a central Italian region. It revealed that while NV is effective in reducing CO ₂ levels during warmer months, mechanical systems are essential in winter to maintain adequate IAQ. However, the performance of CMVs can be hindered by user-related issues such as noise sensitivity and lack of training. The findings highlight the importance of integrating natural and mechanical ventilation to ensure better air quality and thermal comfort throughout the year, supporting healthier and more comfortable learning environments.
Zivelonghi and Giuseppi (2024)	Cfa	Environmental measurement	Air temperature, air relative humidity and CO ₂ concentrations	This study introduced the AulaSicura system, a prototype designed to monitor and improve classroom air quality through real-time measurements and visual/audio alerts. Tested in a northern Italian school over four months, the system proved effective in significantly reducing CO ₂ levels through NV. This improvement in air quality contributes positively to overall thermal comfort and indoor environmental conditions.
Schibuola and Tambani (2021)	Cfa	Environmental measurement, computer simulation and estimation through calculation	Air temperature, ACH, infectious risk and CO ₂ concentration	The study used continuous CO ₂ monitoring and indoor air balance modeling to estimate ACH, highlighting their role in assessing IAQ and infection risk. In naturally ventilated classrooms, results revealed high transmission risk with one asymptomatic individual present. However, increasing ACH through mechanical ventilation reduced viral concentration, especially when combined with moderate mask filtration. Importantly, using energy recovery systems can maintain thermal comfort and minimize energy consumption, offering a practical retrofit solution to enhance ventilation and indoor air quality.

Source: the authors.

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